

The relative standard deviation from ten determinations was found to be $\pm 1.2\%$.

Application to water samples: The proposed method has been successfully employed in the determination of nitrate content of some water samples obtained from local sources of drinking water. The results of the determinations with and without known additions of nitrate are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF NITRATE IN VARIOUS WATER SAMPLES

Sample	Nitrate, mg, l ⁻¹	
	Added	Found
1	0	64
	50	116
2	0	40
	30	73
3	0	95
	10	107

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trithiocarbonates and Mercaptans (Through Trithiocarbonate Formation) with Bismuth(III)

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ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES (RS.CS.S⁻) are the salts of the corresponding trithiocarbonic acids (RS.CS.SH). The compounds find considerable applications^{1,2} in medicine, agriculture and industry. Their vast commercial use necessitates convenient methods for their analysis. A new and rapid extractive spectrophotometric method has

been developed for the determination of these compounds with bismuth(III). The reagent forms yellow insoluble complexes with these compounds. Chloroform is used for extraction which is quantitative within pH 2-8. The absorbance of the yellow extract is measured at 420 nm against a reagent blank. The method has been successfully extended to the determination of mercaptans after their quantitative transformation into the corresponding trithiocarbonates through reaction with carbon disulphide in the presence of alkali. The proposed method is simple, accurate, widely applicable and may be used for the routine analysis of both trithiocarbonates and mercaptans.

Experimental

Organotrithiocarbonates were prepared and purified as described earlier^{1,2}. The purity of the compounds was checked by an iodometric method⁴. Acetate buffer (pH 4.05) was prepared by mixing 2M solutions of acetic acid and sodium acetate in the ratio 8 : 2 (v/v). Mercaptans were distilled before use. Bausch and Lomb spectrophotometer (Spectronic 20) was used for absorbance measurements. Digital pH meter equipped with glass-calomel combination electrode was used for pH measurements.

Aliquots (0.1-1.0 ml) of the solution in water of each trithiocarbonate were transferred with shaking to bismuth(III) nitrate pentahydrate (1 ml, 0.1M in water) and acetate buffer (1 ml, pH 4.05) added. The volume of each solution was made to 10 ml with water. Chloroform (10 ml) was added and the two phases thoroughly equilibrated for 1 min, and then allowed to settle for 1 min. The absorbance of the organic phase was measured spectrophotometrically at 420 nm against a reagent blank, similarly prepared. Calibration curves were prepared in each case. In the determination of mercaptans, potassium hydroxide (2 ml, ~0.05M in water) and carbon disulphide (0.5 ml, ~1M in acetonitrile) were added to aliquots of the solution of mercaptans in acetonitrile. The solution thus obtained was neutralised with acetic acid (~0.1M in water) and to it were added with shaking bismuth(III) nitrate pentahydrate (1 ml, 0.1M in water) and acetate buffer (1 ml, pH 4.05). The volume of each solution was made to 10 ml with water. Further experimental details were the same as described above for trithiocarbonates.

Results and Discussion

The influence of pH on the degree of extraction was studied by extracting the complexes from a series of aqueous solutions buffered in the pH range 2-8. The absorbance was maximal and constant throughout this range. The measurements were, however, made at pH 4.05. One min shaking was required for maximum colour development in the organic phase. The colour of the complex was

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stable for 30 min. The complex shows a strong absorbance at 370 nm which falls steadily to 415 nm and then shows a maximum at 420 nm. The composition of the complex was established spectrophotometrically by the method of continuous variation and mole ratio method. The studies showed that 1 : 3 metal-ligand complex is formed. The molar absorptivities of the bismuth complexes at 420 nm for the potassium salts of ethyl, *n*-hexyl, benzyl, *n*-butyl, *iso*-butyl and dodecyl trithiocarbonic acids are 4.00×10^3 , 4.50×10^3 , 4.69×10^3 , 4.89×10^3 , 4.70×10^3 and 2.58×10^3 l mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, respectively. The concentration ranges per ml of trithiocarbonate solution over which the Beer's law is obeyed are 1.56×10^{-5} to 2.34×10^{-4} , 1.36×10^{-5} to 3.96×10^{-4} , 1.28×10^{-5} to 2.50×10^{-4} , 1.22×10^{-5} to 1.84×10^{-4} , 1.25×10^{-5} to 1.94×10^{-4} , and 2.32×10^{-5} to 4.42×10^{-4} g mol⁻¹ for the potassium salts of ethyl, *n*-hexyl, benzyl, *n*-butyl, *iso*-butyl and dodecyl trithiocarbonic acids, respectively. Acetate, carbon disulphide, urea and thiosulphate do not cause any interference even when present in upto ten-fold excess. Amines, thioureas, sodium carbonate, sodium sulphite, sodium sulphate and alkali halides, however, interfere.

The method has been successfully extended to the determination of mercaptans at microanalytical level after their transformation into the corresponding trithiocarbonates. It has already been shown⁴ that this transformation is rapid and quantitative. The presence of excess carbon disul-

phide (added for transformation) does not interfere in the analysis of mercaptans. The concentration ranges per ml of mercaptan solution over which the Beer's law is obeyed are 1.25×10^{-5} to 1.92×10^{-4} , 0.99×10^{-5} to 4.4×10^{-4} , 0.95×10^{-5} to 3.29×10^{-4} , 0.83×10^{-5} to 1.91×10^{-4} , 0.86×10^{-5} to 2.07×10^{-4} , and 1.56×10^{-5} to 3.74×10^{-4} g mol⁻¹ for ethyl, *n*-hexyl, benzyl, *n*-butyl, *iso*-butyl and dodecyl mercaptans, respectively. Ethyl acetate, urea, dimethyl disulphide and bromobenzene can be tolerated if present in upto 5-fold excess. Xanthates, dithiocarbamates, acrylonitrile, benzaldehyde and glucose, however, interfere.

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